

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Moment Properties of Functionals of Convex Hulls Generated by a Poisson Point Process in Unit Disk

Khamdamov Isakjan, Mamatov Khusniddin and Devyatkin Aleksandr

*University of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chigatay-Aktepa 9549+96W,
100109, Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

khamdamov.isakjan@gmail.com, khmmamatov@gmail.com, Chvtkiu@mail.ru

Keywords: In this paper, we investigate functionals related to the number of vertices, areas, and perimeters of the convex hull generated by an inhomogeneous Poisson point process of the interior unit disk. We utilize the properties of the independence of Poisson law increments and the stationarity of vertex processes associated with the convex hull. We demonstrate the existence of exponential moments for the functionals under consideration. As a result, we conclude that the number of vertices, area, and perimeter of the convex hull possess finite moments of any order.

Introduction

Numerous publications focus on the study of random convex hulls within polygons and on various functionals associated with them. In the 1960s and 70s, a group of researchers, including B. Efron [1], A. Renyi and R. Sulanke [2], and H. Carnal [3], sought to derive asymptotic expressions for the functionals of convex hulls in both bounded and unbounded sets on the plane. The investigation of convex hulls falls under the field of stochastic geometry, and before the research conducted by P. Groeneboom [4], the primary achievement was limited to obtaining asymptotic expressions for the averages of these functionals. It was not until later that asymptotic expressions for the variance were also derived (see [5]). P. Groeneboom [4] made a significant contribution by approximating the binomial point process with a Poisson process, proving the central limit theorem for the number of vertices of a random convex hull. This was specifically when the initial distribution was uniformly concentrated within a convex polygon or ellipse. Here, the existence of exponential moments for the number of vertices, area, and perimeter of the convex hull generated by an inhomogeneous Poisson point process inside the unit disk is proved.

Basic results

Let A be a unit disk centered at point $(0, 1)$.

We consider convex hull C_n generated by the realization $(r_k, \alpha_k), k = 1, 2, \dots$ (in polar coordinate systems, the poles are $(0, b_n)$) of the contraction of an inhomogeneous Poisson point process (i.p.p.p.) $\Pi_{n,\beta}(\cdot)$ in the disk $b_n A$ with intensity

$$\Lambda_{n,\beta}(D) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{b_n}}{2\pi L(b_n)} \iint_D \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left((b_n - r)^\beta L\left(\frac{b_n}{b_n - r}\right) \right) d\alpha dr, & \text{if } D \subset b_n A, \\ 0, & \text{if } D \not\subset b_n A, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here, $\alpha_k \in [-\pi, \pi]$ is uniformly distributed, $L(x)$ is the slowly varying function (s.v.f.) in the sense of Karamata (see, for example, [6]), represented as:

$$L(u) = \exp \left\{ \int_1^u \frac{\varepsilon(t)}{t} dt \right\}, \quad \varepsilon(t) \rightarrow 0, \quad t \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2)$$

and b_n is the smallest root of the equation:

$$nx^{-(\beta+\frac{1}{2})}L(x) = 1. \quad (3)$$

Let $X_i = r_i \sin \alpha_i$, $Y_i = b_n - r_i \cos \alpha_i$.

Next, we assume that $W_n(a) = (X_n(a), Y_n(a))$ for any $a \in [-\pi, \pi]$ – is such a point (X_k, Y_k) of implementation $(X_1, Y_1), (X_2, Y_2), \dots$, for which $r_k \cos(\alpha_k - a)$ takes the maximum value (see Figure 1). Then it follows from the definition that $W_n(a)$ forms a jump-like stationary Markov process, generated by the contraction in $b_n A$ of implementation of i.p.p.p. $\Pi_{n,\beta}(\cdot)$ with intensive measure $\Lambda_{n,\beta}(\cdot)$.

It is worth noting that in reference [4], for the case with uniform intensive measure $\beta = 1$, $L(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{x}$, it was possible to obtain the limit distribution for the number of vertices of the convex hull. The present study is devoted to the asymptotic behavior of the exponential moments of the main functionals of the vertex process for the case $\beta \geq 1$.

Let us denote the number of jumps of the jump-like process $W_n(c)$ within $0 \leq c \leq a$ by $\nu_n(0, a)$, and the length of the broken line connecting the sequence of the states of process $W_n(c)$, $0 \leq c \leq a$ by $l_n(0, a)$.

Let

$$l_n^*(0, a) = b_n \left(\arctan \frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} - \arctan \frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right) - l_n(0, a).$$

Fig.1. An illustration of the vertices $W_n(0), W_n(a_1), \dots$ and the areas $s_n(a_0, a_1), s_n(a_1, a_2), \dots$

Next, let $0 = a_0 < a_1 < a_2 < \dots < a_k \leq a$ be the jump times of process $W_n(c)$, $0 \leq c \leq a$, and $s_n(a_{i-1}, a_i)$ be the area of the figure bounded by lines $(e_{i-1}, w - W_n(a_{i-1})) = 0$, $(e_i, w - W_n(a_{i-1})) = 0$ and circles $x^2 + (b_n - y)^2 = b_n^2$. And let us denote the area of the figure bounded by lines $(e_k, w - W_n(a_k)) = 0$, $(e_a, w - W_n(a_k)) = 0$ and circles $x^2 + (b_n - y)^2 = b_n^2$, by $s_n(a_k, a)$, where $w = (x, y)$, $e_0 = (0, 1)$, $e_i = (-\tan a_i, 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, $e_a = (-\tan a, 1)$ (see Figure 1).

If we assume that

$$s_n(0, a) = s_n(a_0, a_1) + s_n(a_1, a_2) + \dots + s_n(a_k, a),$$

then $s_n(0, a)$ (similar to what was noted in [8,9]) behaves as the sum of a random number of independent random variables. The following theorems to be proved ensure the existence of absolute moments of any power of the functionals under consideration

$$\nu_n(0, a), s_n(0, a) \text{ and } l_n^*(0, a)$$

for $|a| \leq a_0 = \frac{c_0}{\sqrt{b_n}}$.

Here and below, without loss of generality, we assume that c_0, c_1, c_2, \dots are any positive constants whose value may vary from string to string.

Given the similarity of the reasoning, we restrict ourselves to the case $L(x) = 1$, since the demonstrated technique also works for arbitrary slowly varying functions $L(x)$ in the form (2).

Theorem 1. If $|a| \leq a_1 = \frac{c_1}{\sqrt{b_n}}$ for some $c_1 > 0$, then there exists $\tau_1 > 0$ such that

$$E \exp(\tau \nu_n(0, a)) < M_1 \text{ for any } 0 < \tau < \tau_1.$$

Theorem 2. If $|a| \leq a_2 = \frac{c_2}{\sqrt{b_n}}$ for some $c_2 > 0$, then there exists $\tau_2 > 0$ such that

$$E \exp \left(\tau \frac{s_n(0, a)}{\sqrt{b_n}} \right) < M_2 \text{ for any } 0 < \tau < \tau_2.$$

Theorem 3. If $|a| \leq a_1 = \frac{c_3}{\sqrt{b_n}}$ for some $c_3 > 0$, then there exists $\tau_3 > 0$ such that

$$E \exp \left(\tau \sqrt{b_n} l_n^*(0, a) \right) < M_3 \text{ for any } 0 < \tau < \tau_3.$$

Proof of the basic results

Proof of Theorem 1. Let $a > a_0 = 0$. Then from the definition of mathematical expectation, we have:

$$E \{ \exp(\tau \nu_n(0, a) - 1) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0) \} \leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} P(\text{In set } A(0, a, x_0, y_0), \text{ there are } k \text{ points of}$$

$$\text{implementation of i.p.p.p. } \Pi_{n,\beta}(\cdot) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0) \} \leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{\tau k} \frac{(\Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)))^k}{k!}.$$

$$\exp \{ \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) \} = \exp \{ \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) \} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(e^{\tau} \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)))^k}{k!} =$$

$$\exp \{ e^{\tau} \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) \} = \exp \{ \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0))(e^{\tau} - 1) \}.$$

Here $A(0, x_0, y_0)$ – is the domain bounded by lines $y = y_0$ and $x^2 + (y - b_n)^2 = b_n^2$; $A(0, a, x_0, y_0)$ – is the domain bounded by lines $y = \tan a(x - x_0) + y_0$ and $x^2 + (y - b_n)^2 = b_n^2$ (see Figure 2).

Let $y_0 \leq c_0$ be for some constant $c_0 > 0$. Then it follows from the definition of measure $\Pi_{n,\beta}(\cdot)$ that there exists constant $c_1 > 0$ such that

$$\Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) < c_1$$

Hence

$$E \{ \exp(\tau \nu_n(0, a) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0)) \} \leq c_1 \exp(\tau c_2). \quad (4)$$

Let now $y_0 > c_0$. Then there exists some other constant $c_3 > 0$ such that the following inequality holds:

$$\Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) < c_3 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)).$$

From this and from (4), taking into account the independence of the increment of Poisson distribution, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} E \exp(\tau \nu_n(0, a)) &= EE \{ \exp(\tau \nu_n(0, a) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0)) \} \\ &\leq c_1 \iint_{\{b_n A\} \cap \{y_0 \leq c_0\}} \exp\{\tau c_2\} P(W_n(x_0, y_0)) \\ &\in (dx_0, dy_0) + c_2 \iint_{\{b_n A\} \cap \{y_0 > c_0\}} E \{ \exp(\tau \nu_n(0, a) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0)) \} P(W_n(x_0, y_0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq c_3 + c_4 \iint_{b_n A} \exp \{c_5 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0))(e^\tau - 1) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0))\} \|J\| dx_0 dy_0 < \infty$$

for any $0 < \tau < \tau_0$, where $|J|$ – is the Jacobian of the transformation, and τ_0 is chosen such that

$$c_5 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0))(e^\tau - 1) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0)) > -c_6 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, a, x_0, y_0))$$

for some $c_6 > 0$.

The proof of Theorem 1 is complete.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let again $W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0)$.

Then it is not difficult to obtain that

$$E \exp \left(\tau \frac{s_n(0, a)}{\sqrt{b_n}}; y_0 \geq \sqrt{b_n} \right) = o(1).$$

Therefore, we will consider the case that $y_0 < \sqrt{b_n}$.

By the definition of area $s_n(0, a)$ it is easy to see that

$$s_n(0, a) \leq \text{mes} \{A(0, a, x_0, y_0)\},$$

where $\text{mes} \{D\}$ – is the area of domain D . It follows from the definition of domain $A(0, x_0, y_0)$ and $A(0, a, x_0, y_0)$ that

$$\text{mes} \{A(0, a, x_0, y_0)\} = b_n^2 \arcsin \frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} - (b_n - y_0) \sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}. \quad (5)$$

Fig.2. An illustration of the vertices $W_n(0)$ and the areas $A(0, x_0, y_0)$, $A(0, a, x_0, y_0)$.

Using the expansions of trigonometric and inverse trigonometric functions in the neighborhood of zero

$$\sin x = x - \frac{1}{6}x^3 + O(x^5), \quad \tan x = x + \frac{1}{3}x^3 + O(x^5),$$

$$\arcsin x = x + \frac{1}{6}x^3 + O(x^5), \quad \arctan x = x - \frac{1}{3}x^3 + O(x^5)$$

and taking into account (??), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} mes \{A(0, x_0, y_0)\} &= b_n^2 \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} + \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} \right)^3 + O \left(\frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} \right)^5 \right\} - \\ &- b_n \sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2} + y_0 \sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2} = \frac{4\sqrt{2b_n}}{3} y_0^{\frac{3}{2}} + O \left(b_n^{-\frac{5}{4}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, for the area

$$mes \{A(0, a, x_0, y_0)\} \leq b_n^2(a + \gamma) - b_n^2 \sin(a + \gamma),$$

where

$$\gamma = \arcsin \left(\frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} \right) = \frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} + \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} \right)^3 + O \left(\frac{\sqrt{2b_n y_0 - y_0^2}}{b_n} \right)^5,$$

we obtain:

$$mes \{A(0, a, x_0, y_0)\} \leq \frac{b_n^2}{6}(a + \gamma)^3 + O(b_n^2(a + \gamma)^5) = \frac{b_n^2 a^3}{6} + \frac{y_0 \sqrt{2b_n y_0}}{3} + O \left(b_n^2 a^3 + \frac{y_0^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\sqrt{b_n}} \right)$$

see Figure 2.

Consequently, if $y_0 > c_0$, then

$$mes \{A(0, a, x_0, y_0)\} \leq c_1 mes \{A(0, x_0, y_0)\} \leq c_2 \sqrt{b_n y_0^{\frac{3}{2}}} \leq c_3 mes \{A(0, x_0, y_0)\},$$

and if $y_0 \leq c_0$, then

$$mes \{A(0, a, x_0, y_0)\} \leq c_3 \sqrt{b_n}.$$

Hence, considering that $\beta \geq 1$, using the expression Poisson distribution we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} E \exp \left(\tau \frac{s_n(0, a)}{\sqrt{b_n}} \right) &= E E \exp \left(\tau \frac{s_n(0, a)}{\sqrt{b_n}} \middle/ W_n(0) \right) = \\ &= \iint_{b_n \cap \{y_0 \leq c_0\}} E \exp \left(\tau \frac{s_n(0, a)}{\sqrt{b_n}} \middle/ W_n(0) = x_0, y_0 \right) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) + \\ &= \iint_{b_n \cap \{\sqrt{b_n} > y_0 > c_0\}} E \exp \left(\tau \frac{s_n(0, a)}{\sqrt{b_n}} \middle/ W_n(0) = x_0, y_0 \right) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) + o(1) \leq \\ &\leq c_1 + \iint_{b_n \cap \{\sqrt{b_n} > y_0 > c_0\}} E \exp \left(\tau c_2 y_0^{\frac{3}{2}} \right) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq c_1 + \iint_{b_n \cap \{\sqrt{b_n} > y_0 > c_0\}} E \exp(\tau c_3 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0))) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) \\ &\leq c_1 + \iint_{b_n \cap \{\sqrt{b_n} > y_0 > c_0\}} E \exp(\tau c_3 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0))) |J| dx_0 dy_0 < \infty \end{aligned}$$

for any $0 < \tau < \tau_0$. Here, as in the previous case, $|J|$ is the Jacobian of the transformation, and $\tau_0 > 0$ is chosen such that

$$\tau_0 c_3 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)) > -c_4 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0))$$

for some constant $c_4 > 0$.

Theorem 2 is proven.

Fig.3. An illustration of the vertices $W_n(0), \dots, W_n(a)$ and the areas $A(0, x_0, y_0), A(0, a, x_0, y_0)$.

Proof of Theorem 3. Again, we use the expansion into a power series of the inverse trigonometric function

$$\begin{aligned} l_n^*(0, a) &= b_n \left(\arctan \frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} - \arctan \frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right) - l_n(0, a) = \\ &= b_n \left(\frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} - \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} \right)^3 + O \left(\frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} \right)^5 \right) - \\ &- b_n \left(\frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} - \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right)^3 + O \left(\frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right)^5 \right) - l_n(0, a) \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq b_n \left(\frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} - \frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \left(\left(\frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} \right)^3 - \left(\frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right)^3 \right) + \\ &\quad + b_n \left(O \left(\frac{X_n(a)}{b_n - Y_n(a)} \right)^5 + O \left(\frac{X_n(0)}{b_n - Y_n(0)} \right)^5 \right) - (X_n(a) - X_n(0)) \end{aligned}$$

(see Figure 3).

Let $\sqrt{b_n} \geq Y_n(a) \geq c_0$, (the case of $Y_n(a) > \sqrt{b_n}$ is obvious). Then from the last relation we obtain:

$$l_n^*(0, a) \leq \frac{c_1}{\sqrt{b_n}} + \frac{c_2}{\sqrt{b_n}} Y_n^{\frac{3}{2}}(0). \quad (6)$$

Now let $Y_n(a) < c_0$. Then

$$l_n^*(0, a) \leq \frac{c_1}{\sqrt{b_n}}. \quad (7)$$

From (??) and (??), taking into account that $\beta \geq 1$, similarly to the proof of the previous theorem, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} &E \exp \left(\tau \sqrt{b_n} l_n^*(0, a) \right) = E \left\{ E \left(\exp \left(\tau \sqrt{b_n} l_n^*(0, a) \right) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \iint_{(b_n A) \cap (Y \leq c_0)} E \left(\exp \left(\tau \sqrt{b_n} l_n^*(0, a) \right) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0) \right) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) + \\ &+ \iint_{(b_n A) \cap (Y > c_0)} E \left(\exp \left(\tau \sqrt{b_n} l_n^*(0, a) \right) / W_n(0) = (x_0, y_0) \right) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) + \\ &\leq c_2 + c_3 \iint_{b_n \cap \{\sqrt{b_n} > y_0 > c_0\}} E \exp(\tau c_4 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0))) P(W_n(0) \in (dx_0, dy_0)) \\ &\leq c_2 + c_3 \iint_{b_n \cap \{\sqrt{b_n} > y_0 > c_0\}} E \exp(\tau c_4 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0))) |J| dx_0 dy_0 < \infty \end{aligned}$$

for any $0 < \tau < \tau_0$.

Similarly to the previous case, we choose $\tau_0 > 0$ such that

$$\tau_0 c_4 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)) - \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0)) > -c_5 \Lambda_{n,\beta}(A(0, x_0, y_0))$$

for some constant $c_5 > 0$.

Theorem 3 is proven.

Conclusion

Let

$$\mathfrak{S}_n^0 = \sigma \{W_n(c) : c \leq 0\}, \quad \mathfrak{S}_n^{a+} = \sigma \{W_n(c) : c > 0\}.$$

Then, similarly to Lemma 3.3 in [9], the following lemma can be easily proved (see for example [10]).

Lemma 1. If $a = \frac{c_0 k}{\sqrt{b_n}}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, [\log n]$ (c_0 – is an arbitrary constant), then there exists constant $c_1 > 0$, such that

$$|P(A \cap B) - P(A)P(B)| \leq 4 \exp(c_1 k^{2\beta+1-\varepsilon})$$

for any $A \in \mathfrak{S}_n^0$, $B \in \mathfrak{S}_n^{a+}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$.

From Theorems 1 - 3, Lemma 1, and the Ibragimov-Linnik theorem (see, for example, Theorem 18.5.3 in [11]), it follows that stationary processes $\nu_n(0, a)$, $s_n(0, a)$ and $l_n^*(0, a)$ are asymptotic normal.

Acknowledgments

The authors sincerely thanks the editor, the associate editor, and the reviewers for their valuable comments.

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